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Research Article

**A NEW METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF
AXITINIB BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM
BY USING UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY AS PER ICH
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Abstract:

The objective of the present work was to develop a simple, efficient and reproducible spectrophotometric method for the quantitative estimation of Axitinib drug in its active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) form. The developed UV-Visible spectrophotometric method for the quantitative estimation of drug –Axitinib measurement of absorption at a wavelength maximum (λ_{max}) of 260 nm using methanol as diluents. The method was validated as per the ICH guidelines. The proposed method can be successfully applied for the estimation of Axitinib in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The linearity dynamic range 10-70 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and effective mean percentage recoveries were 102.5% and LOQ, LOD values of Axitinib were found to be 1.62 and 5.04 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Key Words: Axitinib, Method Development, Validation, UV-Visible spectrophotometry.***Corresponding Author:****G. Koteswar Rao**Nalanda College of Pharmacy, Charlapally,
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INTRODUCTION:

Axitinib is an Anti-cancer (Anti neoplastic), molecular formula $C_{22}H_{18}N_4OS$, IUPAC name: N-methyl-2-({3-[(E)-2-(pyridin-2-yl) ethynyl]-2H-indazol-6-yl} sulfanyl) benzene-1-carboximidic acid. Axitinib is a second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitor. It selectively inhibits vascular endothelial growth factor receptors (VEGFR-1, VEGFR-2, and VEGFR-3) thus blocking angiogenesis, tumour growth and metastases.

Axitinib has been reported to be 50-450 times more potent than first generation VEGFR inhibitors. According to literature review [12-17] there are very few methods reported for the determination of Axitinib using different instrumental techniques.

Fig. 1: Shows structure of Axitinib

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION:**Standard drugs:**

Axitinib was procured from the INLYTA Pharma.

Chemicals and reagents:

Methanol (FINER chemical LTD), Purified water (Rankem chemicals).

Instruments:

UV (SHIMADZU 1601), Sonicator (Analytical technologies).

Determination of absorption maxima by UV/Visible Spectrophotometry:

Accurately weigh 10 mg of drug in to 10 ml volumetric flask. To this add 10 ml of diluent Methanol and sonicate it and further make up the volume with diluent. From this take 1 ml and make up to 10ml. The solutions were scanned in the range of 200-400 nm in 1cm cell against blank.

Fig.2: Shows UV spectrum of Axitinib

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 100 ml of Methanol, were degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ nylon filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent:

Mobile phase is used as diluent

Standard preparation:

Accurately weigh 10 mg of Axitinib and transfer in to 10ml volumetric flask. Add about 10ml of solvent mixture sonicate to dissolve. Cool the solution to room temperature and dilute to volume with solvent mixture. Transfer 1ml of above solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with diluent.

Sample preparation:

Accurately weigh 10 mg of Axitinib powder and transfer in to 10ml volumetric flask. Add about 10ml of solvent mixture sonicate to dissolve. Cool the solution to room temperature and dilute to volume with solvent mixture. Transfer 1ml of above solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with diluent.

Optimized chromatographic conditions:

Wavelength - 260nm

Solvent - methanol

Method validation:

The following parameters were considered for the analytical method validation of Axitinib in bulk form & tablet dosage form.

System Suitability:

Chromatograph the standard preparations (6 replicate concentrations) and measure the absorbance evaluate the system suitability parameters as directed.

Accuracy:

For accuracy determination, three different concentrations were prepared separately 8%, 100% and 120% for the concentrations of absorbance values are recorded.

Precision:

The standard solution was placed into cuvettes for six times and measured for all six concentrations absorbance values by using max in UV. The %RSD for the area of six replicate concentrations was found to be within the specified limits.

Ruggedness:

As part of the Ruggedness, deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage. Wavelength was varied between plus or minus to. the solutions were made in triplicates and were analyzed the %RSD is determined.

Linearity and range:

Linearity of the analytical method for assay by placing the linearity solutions prepared in the range of 10 μ g to 70 μ g of test concentration, into the cuvettes, covering minimum 7 different concentrations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Standard preparation**

Accurately weigh 10 mg of Axitinib and transfer in to 10ml volumetric flask. Add about 10ml of solventmixture sonicate to dissolve. Cool the

solution to room temperature and dilute to volume with solvent mixture. Transfer 1ml of above solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with diluent.

Fig. 3: Shows UV absorption spectrum of Axitinib standard

Fig. 4: Shows UV absorption spectrum of Axitinib sample Validation

Accuracy:

Average recoveries of Axitinib are 102.85%, 105.70%, 111.42%, at 80%, 100% & 120% concentrations level respectively. The percentage recoveries of the drug are within the limits 98-102%. So, the method is accurate, accuracy data for Axitinib are presented in;

Table 1: Shows Accuracy results of Axitinib

Concentration level	Amount added (mg)	%recovery	Average % recovery
80%	8mg	97.142%	102.85%
	8mg	102.85%	
	8mg	108.57%	
100%	10mg	102.85%	102.37%
	10mg	101.42%	
	10mg	102.85%	
120%	12mg	101.42%	101.42%
	12mg	101.42%	
	12mg	101.42%	

RESULTS:

The accuracy for the average of triplicate in each concentration samples are within the limit.

Table 2: Shows % Recovery of Axitinib

Amount added (mg)	Amount found(mg)	Average % recovery
10mg	10.237mg	102.370%

Precision:

Precision are summarized in **Table No: 3**, respectively. The %RSD values for Precision was less than 2.0%, which indicates that the proposed method is precise.

Table 3: Shows Precision Results of Axitinib

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance of Axitinib
10	0.361
10	0.343
10	0.361
10	0.361
10	0.361
10	0.361
Mean	0.3581
SD	0.000054
%RSD	0.015

Linearity:

The response was found linear over a concentration range of 10-70 µg/mL of Axitinib. The correlation coefficient were found to be 0.9165 for Axitinib. So the method is linear, data is presented in

Table 4: Shows linearity results of Axitinib

S.no	Linerty level	Concentration	Area
1	I	10µg	0.34
2	II	20 µg	0.36
3	III	30 µg	0.42
4	IV	40 µg	0.46
5	V	50 µg	0.67
6	VI	60 µg	0.88
7	VII	70 µg	0.98
Correlation Coefficient			0.9165
Intercept			Y=0.014x+0.001
Slope			0.001

4) Ruggedness:

The Ruggedness of the method was determined by making slight changes in the experimental conditions such as change in the wavelength.

Table 5: Shows Results of Ruggedness**Analyst-1**

S.no	Linerty level	Concentration	Area
1	I	10µg	0.361
2	II	20 µg	0.343
3	III	30 µg	0.3611
4	IV	40 µg	0.3613
5	V	50 µg	0.3612
6	VI	60 µg	0.3612
Correlation Coefficient			0.9165
Intercept			Y=0.014x+0.001
Slope			0.001

Analyst-2

S.no	Linerty level	Concentration	Area
1	I	10µg	0.361
2	II	20 µg	0.343
3	III	30 µg	0.3611
4	IV	40 µg	0.362
5	V	50 µg	0.364
6	VI	60 µg	0.367
Correlation Coefficient			0.9165
Intercept			Y=0.014x+0.001
Slope			0.001

Limit of Detection (LOD)&LOQ:The detection limit is determined by the analysis of samples with known concentration of analyte and by establishing that minimum level at which the analyte can reliably detected , The LOD are calculated from the calibration curve by formula $LOD = 3.3 \times SD/ b$ The quantification limit is generally determined by the analysis of sample with known concentrations of analyte and by establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be quantified with acceptable accuracy and precision, The LOQ are calculated from the calibration curve by formula $LOQ = 10 \times SD/ b$

Table 6: Shows LOD & LOQ results of Axitinib

Parameters	Axitinib
LOD	1.68 μ g/ml
LOQ	5.04 μ g/ml

VALIDATION PARAMETER RESULTS

Table 7: Shows summary of validation parameter Results

S.NO	Parameter	Acceptance criteria	UV
1	%recovery	92-103%	102.37%
2	Linearity range (μ g/ml)	-	10-70(μ g/ml)
3	Correlation Coefficient	NLT 0.999	0.9165
4	Precision	%RSD(NMT 2%)	0.015
5	Intermediate Precision	%RSD(NMT 2%)	0.18
6	Ruggedness	%RSD(NMT 2%)	0.10
7	LOD	-	1.68(μ g/ml)
8	LOQ	-	5.04(μ g/ml)

CONCLUSION:

In the present investigation, we are find out a simple, sensitive, precise and accurate UV-Visible spectroscopy method is developed for the quantitative estimation of axitinib in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms from the literature review.

This method is simple, since diluted samples are directly used without any preliminary chemical derivatization or purification steps.

Axitinib is freely soluble in DMSO and ethanol, methanol and sparingly soluble in water.

This method can be used for the routine determination of axitinib in bulk drug and in Pharmaceutical dosage forms

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